

Arunachal Pradesh: "Unexplored Paradise of India"

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Abstract:- "The Land of Rising Sun" of India and "Land of the Dawn lit mountains" is what Arunachal Pradesh is called. One of India's most isolated, culturally varied, Arunachal Pradesh is located in the northeastern part of India. Visitors are drawn in by the area's captivating natural beauty, tribal culture, and wildlife. The cultural and social communities consist of 26 tribes and approximately 120 sub-tribes, each with a distinct culture and traditions.

Being a distinctive tribal culture, Arunachal is the destination of fairs and festivals, which are an essential component of the local culture. They celebrate all festivals with folk dances and songs along with traditional foods, and indigenous games. The state is having vivid wildlife and unique flora. The potential for the development of tourism in Arunachal Pradesh is massive due to its natural resources and cultural heritage, and it is crucial to look into the very traditional nature of simplicity in the current development scenario. This study will highlight the tourism resources and SWOT analysis of the state's tourism with some recommendations for tourism development

Keywords: - Tribes, Culture, Tourism, Fairs festivals.

I. INTRODUCTION: ARUNACHAL PRADESH "THE LAND OF DAWN – LIT MOUNTAINS"

Tourism is one of the largest sectors in terms of economic development, employment generation, foreign exchange earnings, and managing the balance of payments for a nation. This industry is also considered a smokeless industry. The tourism industry covers a wide range of MSME enterprises, stakeholders, and suppliers. The tourism industry is one of the rapidly growing industries. This industry is helping various nations in their holistic development. Developing countries like India, Thailand, Maldives, etc. are getting great advantages because of the rapidly growing demand for travel.

Tourism is like an elixir for the development of India because it generates direct and indirect income through the consumption of various goods and services by tourists in various destinations. With that government is generating a good amount of taxes from this industry and generating various direct and indirect employment and investment opportunities throughout the nation, specifically in remote or underdeveloped and undeveloped regions.

Tourism focuses on sustainable development in addition to economic development. According to UNWTO "through conservation preservation of natural resources, social development through provision of employment, new business opportunities, and through raising awareness about the aboriginal culture, which includes the ethnicity of the

society, cuisine, handicraft, handloom, etc." Cultural tourism, as defined by UNWTO 2012, is "travel, whose main or concurrent goal is visiting the sites and events whose cultural and historical value has turned them into being a part of the cultural heritage of a community."

Arunachal Pradesh was formerly identified as "North East Frontier Agency (NEFA)" and it became a fully-fledged state of India in 1987. Natural and cultural diversity is abundant in Arunachal Pradesh. In addition to having mountainous terrain with tropical and subtropical forests and a large variety of mammals, reptiles, and birds, this state is home to approximately 126 sub-tribes and 26 major indigenous tribes. It is one of the largest states in North East India, with an area of 83743 sq km.

A tribe is a social class within a culture that symbolizes the anthropological and sociological evolution of the human race. A group of individuals who remain in close contact with one another who claim to be descended from a common ancestor and who also adhere to the same traditional traditions as their predecessors are referred to as a tribe.

One of the Indian states with the widest cultural diversity is Arunachal Pradesh. There are around 126 minor tribes and 26 major tribes in this state. Each tribe has distinct, indigenous cultural elements.

II. ARUNACHAL PRADESH IS DIVIDED INTO 5 CULTURAL ZONES

- **Tawang and Kameng's regions are where we can find the majority of people from the Buddhist Monpa, Sherdupen, Aka, Miji, and Khowa tribes.**
- **East Kameng and Lower and Upper Subansiri. Mostly people from Nyishi, Bangini, Sulung, Apatans, Nas, Tagin, Mikir, and Hill Miri tribes.**
- **Upper Subansiri and the East and West Siang districts, Adi and Tagin are the major tribes along with the 15 major sub-tribes of Adi reside in that region.**
- **The Dibang Valley, lower Dibang Valley, and Lohit regions consist of major tribes including Khamti and Mishmi tribes.**
- **Tirap and Changlang regions include tribes like Nocte, Wancho, Tangsa, and Singpho.**

III. TRIBES OF ARUNACHAL PRADESH

The state is bestowed with natural scenic beauty along with that state is having aboriginal culture. Tourists can witness unique culture which is different from rest of the India. The state is having different tribes and each tribe is having different culture, tradition, and lifestyle which is the major attention seekers for tourists. Tribal tourism is one of the forms of tourism which can enhance and promote sustainable

tourism and sustainable growth in the region. "Major tribes of Arunachal Pradesh are Adi, Apatani, Bugun, Hrusso, Singpho, Mishmi, Monpa, Nyishi, Sherdukpen, Tagin, Khamti, Wancho, Nocte, Yobin, Khamba, etc." (Kumar, 2018)

IV. MAJOR FESTIVALS OF ARUNACHAL PRADESH

Fairs and festivals are the prism of rich culture and traditions. This represents multiple values, morals, belief systems, and customs of the community. Fairs and festivals are one of the many ways to transfer cultural information and values to future generations. Most of the festivals in Arunachal Pradesh revolve around the cultivation and harvesting of crops. Festivals of the states also vary from tribe to tribe and all the tribes are having their ways to celebrate and enjoy festivals which include folk dances, singing, aboriginal games, food, etc. The state has also initiated various festivals which are motivated by the modern world like music festivals, carnivals, etc., and also has a few festivals which are developed by the government to attract tourists like river festivals, summer and winter carnivals etc.

Table 1: Major Festivals Of Arunachal Pradesh

Sr. No	Festival	Name of Tribe	Month	District
1	Pangsua Pass Winter Festival		January	Changlang
2	Si-Donyi	Tagin	January	Upper – Subansiri
3	Lossar	Monpa and Sherdukpen	February	West – Kameng
4	Boori Boot	Hill – Miri	February	Upper – Subansiri
5	Shapawng Yawng Manau Poi	Singpho	February	Changlang
6	Reh	Idu Mishmi	February	Lower Dibang Valley
7	Oriah	Wancho	February	Tirap
8	Tamladu	Taroon and Kamman Mishmi	February	Anjaw and Lohit
9	Nyokum	Nyishi	February	Papum Pare, Kurung Kumey, Lower – Subansiri, East – Kameng
10	Khan	Miji	Feb/March	West – Kameng
11	Aran	Adi	March	East – Siang
12	Mopin	Galo	April	West – Siang
13	Gomkum gompa	Sulung	April	Papum Pare, Kurung Kumey, Lower – Subansiri, East – Kameng
14	Sangken	Khampti	April	Lohit
15	Dree	Apatani	July	Lower – Subansiri
16	Chalo-Loku	Nocte	November	Tirap
17	Solung	Adi	September	East – Siang
18	Ziro Music festival		September	Lower – Subansiri
19	Siang River festival		December	West – Siang

(Deep Jyoti Gurung, 2003)

V. WILDLIFE OF ARUNACHAL

The vivid flora and fauna of the state make it a paradise for wildlife photographers, wildlife lovers, and nature lovers. 93.03% of the geographical area of Arunachal Pradesh is covered by forest which is the habitat of the clouded leopard, red panda, and gibbons, as well as a wide range of butterflies, birds, orchids, and therapeutic plants. The state is having 10 Wildlife Sanctuaries and 2 National Parks Namdapha National Park and Mouling National Park (Ministry of Environment, 2023)

VI. TOURIST CIRCUITS OF ARUNACHAL PRADESH

Department of Arunachal Tourism identified 13 major tourist circuits which consist of multiple locations in the state with specific themes, and geographic and cultural features. These circuits provide a closer view of the state's cultural and natural heritage.

- Tezpur – Bhalukpong – Bomdila - Tawang
- Itanagar – Ziro – Daporijo – Aalo - Pasighat
- Pasighat – Jengging – Yingkiong - Tuting
- Tinsukia - Tezu - Hayuliang
- Margherita – Miao – Namdhapa - Vijaynagar
- Dibrugarh – Deomali – Hakanjuri - Khonsa
- Dibrugarh - Kanubari - Longding
- Tezpur – Seijosa - Bhalukpong

- Ziro – Palin – Nyapin – Sangram - Koloriang
- Doimukh - Sagalee - Pake Kessang - Seppa
- Aalo - Mechuka
- Daporijo – Taliha – Siyum - Nacho
- Jairampur – Manmao – Nampong – Pangsau Pass

Source (DOT, 2023) **Department of Tourism Arunachal Pradesh**

VII. ARRIVAL FORMALITIES IN ARUNACHAL PRADESH

Natural and cultural diversity makes this state different from other states. As this state is having an aboriginal culture government imposed few conditions to enter the state. Any Indian National or Foreign national who wants to enter the state needs to get a permit which is issued by government authorities. For Indian nationals it is called ILP (Inner Line Permit) which is valid for 14 days and foreign nationals it is called PAP or RAP (Protected Area Permit / Restricted Area Permit) (DOT, 2023)

Table 2: Tourist arrival in Arunachal Pradesh

Year	Total Tourist Arrival
2012	132345
2013	125461
2014	335974
2015	352067
2016	385875
2017	444005
2018	512436
2019	555639
2020	42871
2021	102915

Source: -Ministry of Tourism Statistics (Tourism, India tourism statistic at a glance 2023, 2023)

VIII. HURDLES IN THE GROWTH OF TOURISM IN ARUNACHAL PRADESH

- **Restrictions to travelers:** No tourist is allowed to travel without ILP, RAP, or PAP
- Poor Infrastructure
- Lack of proper marketing
- Poor telecommunication facilities
- Poor Accessibility (poor road conditions) and limited flights.
- Insurgency in some border areas
- Lack of professional manpower in the hospitality sector

IX. SWOT ANALYSIS OF ARUNACHAL PRADESH TOURISM

SWOT analysis of Arunachal Tourism is based on empirical research and past experiences of the state. This analysis assists the state to formulate or add some recommendations to the state tourism policies and also helps in following sustainable tourism practices, and protect the state's natural and cultural heritages which are the unique features of the state along with future opportunities. This analysis also highlights the major concerns which are faced by the tourists so that those concerns or hurdles are eradicated by the concerned authorities.

- **Strengths:** The biggest strength of the state is its aboriginal culture and its natural heritage. The state's diverse ethnicity, vegetation, and fauna are the backbone of the state. The state lies in the eastern part of the Himalayas which provides pleasant weather. The state is also having a great essence of generosity towards tourists.
- **Weakness:** Connectivity within the state is a major concern especially road connectivity, unplanned infrastructural development, low human resource development and utilization of manpower and lack of awareness regarding sustainable tourism practices are the major flaws in the state.
- **Opportunities:** There is special emphasis given by the Government of India to the development of tourism in the North Eastern region. The development of Hollongi Airport, advanced landing grounds in various districts, and Naharlagun railway station will provide endless future opportunities in tourism. Various schemes are governed by the Government of India like Swadesh Darshan (Tourism, Scheme Guidelines For Swadesh Darshan, 2022), Ude Desh ka Aam Naagrik (UDAN), Pilgrimage Rejuvenation and Spiritual Augmentation Drive (PRASAD) (Tourism, Scheme Guidelines For Prasad, 2022), North East Special Infrastructure Development Scheme (NESIDS).
- **Threats:** The other side of tourism development is destruction and overutilization of resources. Tourism is also having an adverse effect on society which promotes acculturation, Commodification, standardization, etc. Imbalance in nature and the environment is also a threat in front of the state.

X. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AND THE IMPROVEMENT IN TOURISM SERVICES

- **Enhance Local Participation:** “Local community participate can enhance the contribution towards the economic development, sustainable conservation, quality of life”. (S. Mostafa Rasoolimaesh, 2016) To develop tourism in any region the participation of the local community is one of the most important attributes. With the help of local participation, we can ensure much better services and authentic and reliable experiences for tourists. In tribal tourism aboriginal culture, knowledge and all components of culture are the major attraction for the tourist. More participation from the local community provides economic benefits to the local society and tourists will get unforgettable experiences. More local participation also ensures community capacity development.
- **Tourism Awareness:** “Destination selection behavior consist of psychology of tourist they select destination when they are aware about destination, desires, action, and reaction. If consumer is not aware, tourist may skip the destination.” (Kirkpatrick, 1982) Tourism understanding or awareness among the communities plays a vital role in the development of tourism in any destination. “To be a successful destination a destination must have awareness, positive image for new visitor and if visitor get satisfied first time visitor is going to be repeat

visitor” (Pizam, 1995) People must have information regarding policies run by the government, schemes for destination development, and various tourism resources. “Tourism activities can only be sustainable if implemented with a common understanding and consensus-based approach to development”. (Mohinder Chand, 2012).

- **Strong marketing Strategies:** Tourism marketing is a crucial component for the success of any tourist destination for tourism promotions both public and private stakeholders must opt for advanced marketing strategies like e-marketing or digital marketing. Digital marketing helps to attract both domestic as well as international tourists to the state. “Destination marketing strategies is proving huge assistance to get customers in tourism industry. Multiple media sources are used to grab the attentions of tourists.” (Sharma, 2013)
- **Encouraging and promoting green tourism practices:** Cultural and natural environment of Arunachal Pradesh is fragile. To conserve the natural and manmade resources of the state local entrepreneurs and tourists must encourage practicing green tourism practices. It will enhance the economy of the state and conserve and protect the environment and resources of the area. Practices like waste management, ecotels, home stays, eco-friendly transportation, etc. “There is need of prioritizing the learning of and local communities regarding sustainable and eco tourism practices. Both local communities and tourist need to understand that without the cooperation of both no destination can survive environmentally and economically” (Niedziółka, 2014)
- **Highlighting Tribal tourism with Eco-Tourism** "Travelling to relatively undisturbed or uncontaminated natural areas with the specific objective of studying, admiring, and enjoying the scenery and its wild plants and animals, as well as any existing cultural manifestations (both past and present) found in these areas" (LASCURAIN, 1987) Eco-tourism enhances the participation of the local community in tourism activity and also motivates tourists to perform ecotourism practices. High involvement of the local community and direct and indirect employment to the local communities provides economic as well as social benefits.
- **Sustainable Infrastructure Development:** “Sustainable infrastructure development is equilibrium between economic development and ecological environmental regeneration.” (Berawi, 2016). Accessibility is the component of tourism that enables tourists to reach their destination. Government must have proper and sustainable infrastructure to cater to the needs of tourists. Govt. needs to ensure proper waste management and proper maintenance of existing natural and manmade heritage.

XI. CONCLUSION

Arunachal Pradesh is having all the resources which are require being an appropriate destination for tourists. Even for the millennial this destination is having a variety of attractions. Its geographical location and physiographic features make this destination appropriate for adventure seekers, its flora and fauna are also a key attraction for wildlife lovers and tourists who are curious to learn new things or want to experience aboriginal culture this destination is paradise for those tourists. Though the state is having all the required resources only the right promotional strategies, sustainable infrastructure, and local community involvement is needed.

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